

About the Guide

Welcome to The Carpentries TopicBox group – [Topicbox](#) is used for announcements and richer discussions, which, while possible, would be too crowded and unsuited for Slack. It is also a preferred communication channel for members seeking to limit the number of channels they follow.

If you are new to TopicBox or simply overwhelmed by the prospect of yet another TopicBox group, here are some quick pointers to help you configure and use the tool in a way that works best for you. They are in 3 key areas:

1. Configuring your account
2. Notification settings
3. Communicating with others

1. Configuring your account

A. Profile

Go to <https://carpentries.topicbox.com> and create a profile.

The screenshot shows a login form titled "Log In" on a light gray background. The form is a white rounded rectangle containing the following elements:

- The title "Log In" centered at the top of the form.
- An "Email" label above a text input field.
- The text "email@example.com" entered in the input field.
- A red three-dot menu icon in the top right corner of the input field.
- A checked checkbox followed by the text "Keep me logged in".
- A green "Next" button at the bottom right of the form.

Log In

We have emailed a single-use code to:

test@test.com

Enter the code we sent you:

XXXXXX

Verify

test@test.com - [Switch user](#)

The Carpentries
elletjes@gmail.com

 News Center

 Groups

The Carpentries

Welcome to The Carpentries Mailing lists. We have many channels of threaded discussion here. The most general and broad discussions about teaching, pedagogy, technology and tools happen in the discuss-* mailing lists. Conversations with local and regional communities happen in the local-* mailing lists.

Other lists break out in to specific tools, localities, disciplines and sub-communities. For more information about the various sub-communities and the vocabulary we use to describe them check out our about community info page: <https://carpentries.org/community>

This is an open, kind, and respectful community. Users of this system are expected to follow our Code of Conduct: https://docs.carpentries.org/topic_folders/policies/code-of-conduct.html

This is your organization's News Center

B. Join groups

Once you have successfully created a profile, you can join public groups. Join public groups by clicking on the **Groups** button and then the **Groups to join button** at the top of the Groups page. Private groups can only be joined by accepting an email invitation or being directly added as a member by a group administrator or organisation owner.

Below is a list of selected groups found on The Carpentries TopicBox:

Open Groups

- [Discuss](#)—This group is for general discussion of Carpentries' teaching practices, community activities, and concerns. **Community-relevant posts are open to the community.**
- [Discussion Hosts](#) - The community of Instructors that host [community discussion sessions](#). **Community-relevant posts are open to the community.**
- [Instructors](#) - An admin-only list where opportunities for badged Instructors and Helpers to teach are announced.
- [Opportunities](#)—This mailing list posts relevant opportunities for work, fellowships, grants, etc., for The Carpentries community members.
- [Community Development Program](#) - This is a mailing list for members of The Carpentries community who are currently leading or are interested in leading a

subcommunity. We define a subcommunity as a group of community members serving in the same role within the organisation, located in the same geographic region, or who come together because they share common interests. The Community Development Program will provide resources and professional development to support you in this role.

- local-* - A list for discussing The Carpentries in our local and regional communities.

These are open groups.

- [Australia and New Zealand](#)
- [Africa](#)
- [Bay Area](#)
- [Bangladesh](#)
- [Boston](#)
- [Colorado](#)
- [California Libraries](#)
- [Davis, California](#)
- [Germany](#)
- [Heidelberg](#)
- [India](#)
- [Lansing](#)
- [Latino America](#)
- [Merced](#)
- [Middle East and North Africa](#)
- [Nordic](#)
- [Puerto Rico](#)
- [Seattle](#)
- [Southeast US Library Carpentry](#)
- [Southern California](#)
- [Southwest United States](#)
- [University of California](#)
- [UK](#)
- [Vancouver, Canada](#)
- [Washington, DC](#)

Closed Groups

- [Instructor Trainers](#) - A list of topics related to the community of Trainers that prepare new Instructors in teaching Data, Software, and Library Carpentry lessons. **For Instructor Trainers only.**
- [CarpentryCon*](#) - This group will be for the planning group to execute CarpentryCon.
- [Maintainers](#) - A list of topics related to the maintenance of Carpentries lessons. **For Maintainers only.**

2. Notification settings

You can control how often you receive an activity summary in your group delivery preferences.

The screenshot shows the TopicBox interface. On the left is a dark sidebar with the user's profile 'The Carpentries' and a 'Groups' button highlighted with a red box and a '1'. The main area shows '1 selected' groups under 'Your Groups'. A group named 'Community Development Program' is selected, with a red box and a '3' next to its tick box. A 'Delivery Options' dropdown menu is open, showing three options: 'Email it to me', 'Include it in my daily summary' (selected), and 'I'll view it on the web; don't email me'. A red box and a '4' are next to the dropdown. A search bar with 'Find a group' and a red box and a '2' is also visible.

Use the following steps to set up your activity summary:

1. Click on **GROUPS**
2. Find the group you would like to set up an activity summary for (you can search for more than one)
3. Select the tick box (you can select more than one)
4. Click on Delivery Options and choose which activity summary you would like.

Read more: <https://www.topicbox.help/hc/en-us/articles/360055336873-Daily-summary>

3. Communicating with others

Creating a Topic

<https://www.topicbox.help/hc/en-us/articles/360055336913-Creating-a-topic>

Viewing a Topic

<https://www.topicbox.help/hc/en-us/articles/360053550314-Viewing-a-topic>

New Topics: Staying Up to Date

<https://www.topicbox.help/hc/en-us/articles/360053550374-New-topics-staying-up-to-date>

Searching for a Topic

<https://www.topicbox.help/hc/en-us/articles/360055336953-Searching-for-a-topic>

Acknowledgements

The content of this guide was based upon the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement “TopicBox quick start guide” by Lou Woodley and Katie Pratt, licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) license.

The original guide is cited as: Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2020) Slack quick start guide. Woodley and Pratt doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3763730